

Mumps Cases Reported in Tertiary Hospital During 2017-2018 in Baghdad, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Mumps is a disease caused by the mumps virus. It spread from human-to-human via direct contact or by airborne droplets. Initial signs and symptoms often include fever, muscle pain, headache, poor appetite, and feeling generally unwell. This is then usually followed by painful swelling of one or both parotid salivary glands

Method: A cross sectional study conducted in Al-Yarmouk teaching hospital during the period from January 2017 through December 2018. All patients of different ages and from both sexes diagnosed with mumps were included in this study.

Results: Most infections 72.1% occur in age groups ≥ 15 years. The high percentage of cases occur in males (62.5%). Cases reported among the vaccinated patients in all age groups, 16 patients (55.2%) of children were ≤ 14 years of age. Those who don't know about their vaccination state constitute (77.3%) of patient aged ≥ 15 . There was a significant association between immunization state and age. High percent of infection in 2017 were in March (14.4%), April (10.6%) and January (7.7%) while lowest rates of infection were showed in year 2018 for the same period.

Conclusion: The role of vaccination was limited in protection of patients against mumps disease; third booster dose of mumps vaccine is recommended to prevent future epidemics.

Keywords: Mumps, Baghdad, vaccination.

Introduction

Mumps is a disease caused by the mumps virus⁽¹⁾. It spread from human-to-human via direct contact or by airborne droplets. Initial signs and symptoms often include fever, muscle pain, headache, poor appetite,

and feeling generally unwell⁽²⁾⁽³⁾. This is then usually followed by painful swelling of one or both parotid salivary glands⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾. Symptoms typically occur 16 to 18 days after exposure and resolve after 7 to 10 days⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾. About one third of people have mild or no symptoms, these are often more severe in adults than in children⁽²⁾. Immunity is generally life long and develop after either inapparent or clinical infections⁽⁵⁾. Live mumps vaccines are available as monovalent mumps vaccine, bivalent measles-mumps (MM) vaccine, and trivalent measles-mumps-rubella (MMR) vaccine. Following the use of mumps vaccine in the USA in the late 1960s, disease incidence declined dramatically, and by the 1980s very few cases were reported⁽⁶⁾. However, large,

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sporadic mumps outbreaks began to appear globally, involving a high percentage of persons with a history of vaccination⁽⁷⁾. In Iraq, the total number of mumps' cases reported in 2003 was 7051 case. The number of cases increased to 11821 during January to April 2004. There was a dramatic reduction in the number of cases (less than 1500) reported in the following 8 months (May to December 2004)⁽⁸⁾.

Studying mumps antibodies, Quasim (2010) in Mousal city found seropositivity against mumps virus among different age groups was 68%⁽⁹⁾. Study done by Baiee and Hatif (2018) they found that about half of the patients (56%) were vaccinated against the mumps disease in two districts located in the southern region of Babylon governorate⁽¹⁰⁾. Park et al. (2007) examine the discriminate between primary and secondary vaccine failure in a highly vaccinated population for mumps after an outbreak of mumps occurred in Gyeonggi, Korea in 2006⁽¹¹⁾. Vaccination coverage during the years 2008 and 2009 was 92.4% and 93.6% respectively indicating a highly vaccinated population in the village in Orange County in New York State where the mumps outbreak occurred⁽¹²⁾. WHO recommends immunization coverage of 90% to prevent outbreaks of mumps⁽¹³⁾.

Aim of Study: The current study designed to determine the rate of occurrence of mumps in 2017-2018(minor outbreak) in Baghdad.

Patients and Method

A cross sectional study conducted in Al-Yarmouk teaching hospital during the period from January 2017 till December 2018.

All patients of different ages and from both sexes diagnosed with mumps were included in this study. Data were obtained from the hard and soft records in the “Communicable Disease Control Program”/public healthunit.

Data were grouped tabulated and presented as frequencies ant percentages Chi-square test was performed using statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 24.0. P-value of 0.05 and less was considered as significant.

Results

The total number of cases were 104, the range was 2-68 years, and the mean and standard deviation of age was (27.08±15.287).

Table-1 showed the older age group represented the largest one 75(72.1%), they were at the age group of 15 years and older. The smallest age group 29(27.9%) were of the less and equal 14 years. Male were affected more than female in this study (62.5% and 37.5% respectively). Higher percentage of occupation were the employed 51(49%) while the lowest rate was in those without working 7(6.7%).

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to residency

Figure-1 represented the residency of the patients where 89.4% came from urban area, 7.7% came from suburban, and the remaining 2.9% were from rural areas.

Table 1: Main characteristics of the study sample

Variables (N=104)	N	%
Age Groups		
≤14	29	27.9
≥15	75	72.1
Gender		
Male	65	62.5
Female	39	37.5
Occupation		
Employee	51	49.0
Worker	9	8.7
Not working	7	6.7
Student	26	25.0
Child	11	10.6

Bar chart in figure-2 shows that the highest frequency of cases in year 2017 occurred in March (14.4%) and the lowest in December was not cases registered and most cases in the year 2018 in October, November and December were the same percent (4.8%) and lowest in June was (0%).

Figure 2: Distribution of cases according to months in years 2017 & 2018

Cases of mumps reported among the immunized patients in all the age groups, 16 patients (55.2%) of children were ≤14 years of age. For those aged ≥15 the rate of occurrence of mumps was higher among the Don't know about their vaccination constitute (77.3%). Significant association between immunization state

and age was (P = 0.002). Patients of both sexes had the infection in spite of being vaccinated male (33.8%) and female (25.6%). Although the relationship between immunization state and infection was not significant (P = 0.653) (table-2).

Table 2: Distribution of immunization status according to age and gender

Variables	Immunization								P-value
	Yes		No		Don't Know		Total		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Age Groups									
≤ 14	16	55.2	1	3.4	12	41.4	29	100	0.002*
≥ 15	16	21.3	1	1.3	58	77.3	75	100	
Total	32	30.8	2	1.9	70	67.3	104	100	
Gender									
Male	22	33.8	1	1.5	42	64.6	65	100	0.653
Female	10	25.6	1	2.6	28	71.8	39	100	
Total	32	30.8	2	1.9	70	67.3	104	100	

*Statistically significant

Table 3 showed the highest rate of recorded mumps cases was during Springs (39.4%) followed by Autumn at a rate of (23.1%) which is very close to that during Winter (22.1%) the lowest rate was during Summer (15.2%). Children and adult encounter the infection mainly in Spring (41.4%) and (38.7%) respectively.

The highest infection rate among male was in Spring 44.6%) and among female was during Autumn (35.9%). There was no significant relationship between season of recorded cases in one hand and the age and gender in the other hand P=0.173 and P=0.081 respectively.

Table 3: Occurrence of cases in relation to seasons

Variables	Season										P-value
	Springe		Summer		Autumn		Winter		Total	%	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
Age Groups											
≤ 14	12	41.4	3	10.3	4	13.8	10	34.5	29	100	0.173
≥ 15	29	38.7	13	17.3	20	26.7	13	17.3	75	100	
Total	41	39.4	16	15.4	24	23.1	23	22.1	104	100	
Gender											
Male	29	44.6	12	18.5	10	15.4	14	21.5	65	100	0.081
Female	12	30.8	4	10.3	14	35.9	9	23.1	39	100	
Total	41	39.4	16	15.4	24	23.1	23	22.1	104	100	

Discussion

Age, gender and occupation: Three quarter of patients in this study were adult, age ≥ 15 years old. This agree with Jasminka et al. study in 2015 in Vojvidina, Serbia who found most of their study samples occurs in age groups of 15 29 years of old (14). But disagree with Areej study in 2018 in Baghdad who found most of the patients were in the age group below 15 years of age (15).

Regarding the gender, the results of our study demonstrated that males affected more than females, this could be explained by that male more moving outside doors and they usually engaged in different types of work leading to high person to person contact. This findings went with the findings of Areej, in 2018 (15) and with Jasminka et al. in 2015 in Vojvidina (14).

Regarding the occupation, About half of the sample were employee, Yu G et al. in 2018 found in his study in Guangxi, China that slightly higher than half of the patients were students (16).

Residence: Regarding the residence, the results demonstrated that the higher percentage of exposure in urban areas (89.4%), Baiee HA, Weli H, 2017 in Babylon province, Iraq which agree with this study who found most of study samples in urban more than rural areas (10).

Time (Month` s exposure): The results of this study revealed that the higher percentage of exposure was in March 2017 followed by the percentage in October, November and December 2018, Baiee and Hatifin 2017 in Babylon province, Iraq showed results that disagree with this study, they found most of most of cases were

in January (10) Again disagree with Areej in 2018, who depict most cases occurred in January (15).

Immunization Status: Regarding immunization status the results illustrated that the higher percent of cases occurred among immunized patients in age groups ≤14 years, this disagree with Jasminka et al. in 2015, Serbia which depict high cases occurred in age groups 20 - 29 and 15 - 19 years of old respectively (14). Also disagree with Whelan et al. in 2010 in Netherlands who found most cases recorded in cases aged 22 years of old vaccinated with two doses (17).

We found that infection affect vaccinated patients of both sex with male affected slightly more than female. This in agreement with Orlikova et al. 2016 in Czech Republic which demonstrate higher males affected than females (18).

Season occurrence with age and gender: during spring season highest number of cases reported in age group of ≤ 14 years this in contrast to Yi-Chien et al. 2015 in Taiwan which illustrated that most cases in summer season (19).

Regarding to the gender the results illustrates that the higher percent of males cases occurred in spring but the higher percent of female cases occurred in autumn which agree with Sawsan and Al-Hasnawi, 2018 in Karbala, Iraq which showed that most males infected in March (spring) season while most females in the last of November (autumn) and first December (winter) (20).

Ethical Issue: A formal clearance was taken from the Ethical Committee of Al-Yarmouk teaching hospital. All used data were confidentially kept for the purpose of the study.

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Conflict of Interest: We declare that there was no any conflict of interest.

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